

MULTI-VECTOR RESEARCH ON IMPROVING STUDENTS' COLLABORATIVE SKILLS IN HIGHER EDUCATION BASED ON PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES

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Abstract. The purpose of the thesis is to substantiate the effectiveness of the implementation of a collaborative approach in the formation of team competence in the system of higher and additional professional education.

Keywords: territories of advanced socio-economic development, personnel training.

INTRODUCTION

Support for domestic producers, through the creation of Territories of Advanced Social and Economic Development, has as its ultimate goal the creation of powerful domestic production and in this sense is one of the key elements of import substitution policy. If used correctly, such support can become an effective measure for the development of the national economy. At the same time, there are systemic problems in the industry that require an unconditional solution, including improving the quality of the human resources of specialists in the mechanical engineering industry.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In her work, A. Neretina reveals the possibilities of the project method as an effective means of developing team competence [1]. E.V. Bolgarina in her study believes that the main motive encouraging students to effective teamwork can be real projects, for which students have already formed basic knowledge sufficient to obtain a clear idea of the final results, and not far-fetched educational projects [2]. V.S. Okuneva believes that work on a project should be enriched with interactive technologies. This develops communication skills, since in order to achieve the team's goals it is necessary to regularly communicate and establish a constructive dialogue with team members [3]. A similar opinion is shared by A.D. Nikolaeva and A.D. Malysheva, noting that the success of developing the competence of "working in a team" depends on the creation of a developing environment using communication technologies [4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

However, the analysis conducted by the authors shows that there is a shortage of developed methods for developing teamwork skills, including in training in mechanical engineering specialties.

Summarizing the experience of implementing collaborative learning in pedagogy and personal experience in organizing group work, we believe that the process of forming team competence in future engineers should include the following stages:

- 1) Creating professional significance and personal value of teamwork in students;
- 2) Taking into account the individual personal qualities and value orientations of each team member when organizing group work;
- 3) Implementing the role of the teacher not as a translator of ready-made knowledge, but as a teacher-curator, guiding students to make decisions by realizing the potential of the group as a whole and each of its members individually;
- 4) Clear criteria for assessing the results of teamwork, reflection of one's own activities.

Let us consider these stages in more detail.

1. Creating professional significance and personal value of teamwork in students

As a rule, a future engineer needs a lot of time after leaving the university to adapt to the conditions of professional activity.

The presence of professionally significant value orientations in a graduate ensures his conscientious attitude to the chosen profession, causes the desire and aspiration to get involved in professional activity as quickly as possible. This becomes possible if the educational process is close to real professional activity. In this regard, all tasks performed by students in special disciplines should be related to specific production problems or be of an applied nature.

2. Taking into account the individual personal qualities and value orientations of each team member when organizing group work

During team work, students experience strong emotional experiences. They arise at the moment of task distribution, in the process of choosing various alternative solutions to a problem, in preparation for the defense of a project. All team members are responsible for the result of team work, and confidence in future success unites the participants. During the work, students have to deal with the individual uniqueness of each group member, show respect and tolerance to

each other, and provide support. One of the conditions for successfully achieving the set goals is the presence of psychological and emotional comfort in the team.

A positive result of this approach to teaching is possible if the following stages of organizing teamwork are observed.

I. Preparatory.

At this stage, the teacher introduces the team members to the rules of teamwork and gives the task. Students can independently develop rules-agreements in the form of instructions that they must follow.

Example of instructions.

1. Respect the opinion of each team member, allow him to express his point of view to the end, do not interrupt.
2. Build work on the basis of mutual assistance.
3. Independently try to solve emerging problems and only when necessary, ask the teacher for help.
4. Strictly adhere to the time limit.
5. Agreedly distribute roles within the team.

After signing the instructions, the teacher introduces the team members to the task. The nature of the educational task is determined by the pedagogical goals:

- the task must correspond to the capabilities and abilities of students;
- must have several solutions, stimulating the development of various ideas and ways to solve it;
- should be designed in such a way that its implementation equally involves all team members;
- teams can be given the same tasks and compete in several categories – the most non-standard solution, creative approach, etc.

II. Teamwork.

After receiving the task, the team members independently (possibly with the support of the teacher) distribute it among themselves. Team members must jointly determine the scope of work and the area of responsibility of each performer, set a time schedule.

Each team member can express their hypothesis, version, their position on the task. The rest of the team must show respect for someone else's point of view and listen carefully to their colleague. All opinions must be recorded and a single solution must be jointly developed.

CONCLUSION

Thus, one of the promising areas for improving the quality of training and retraining of specialists is the introduction of a collaborative approach into the educational process. The conducted study of psychological and pedagogical literature allowed us to come to the conclusion that collaborative learning has great potential in developing team competence. Firstly, it guides future graduates of a technical university to work in an innovative mode, motivating them to find a non-standard solution. Secondly, working in a team, the skill of listening and understanding others, expressing one's point of view, finding a compromise develops, which corresponds to the modern requirements of the labor market.

References:

1. Benne K.D., Sheats P. Functional Roles of Group Members // Journal of Social Issues. 1948. no. 4 (2). pp. 41-49. DOI: 10.1111/j.1540-4560.1948.tb01783.x
2. Brannick M.T., Prince C., Salas E. Can PC-based systems enhance teamwork in the cockpit? // The International Journal of Aviation Psychology. 2005. no. 15(2). pp. 173-187
3. Burke C.S., Fiore. S.M., Salas. E. The role of shared cognition in enabling shared leadership and team adaptability // Shared Leadership: Reframing the Hows and Whys of Leadership. 2003. pp. 103-122. DOI: 10.4135/9781452229539.n5
4. Cruz K., Pinto J. Team Focus in Focus: Its Implications for Real Teams and Their Members // Journal of work and organizational psychology-revista de psicologia del trabajo y de las organizaciones. 2019. 35 (2). pp. 123-133 DOI: 10.5093/jwop2019a14
5. Eva Imania Eliasa. Increasing Values of Teamwork and Responsibility of The Students. Through Games: Integrating Educational Character in Lectures // Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences 123. 2014. pp. 196-203. DOI: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.1415
6. Musurmonova O, Baubekova G. Uzbek folk pedagogy. Tashkent. 2000;320.
7. Aynisa, M. (2018). Improvement of the pedagogical mechanisms of the family and educational institutions in the development of the spiritual culture of adolescents of social and legal risk groups. Проблемы педагогики, (1 (33)), 5-7.